

Post-Occupancy Evaluation of School Building Performance

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ABSTRACT

School buildings are multifunctional structures that accommodate several functions and activities. Such activities require different environmental and functional characteristics for their hosting spaces. This comprehensive research aims to establish a multi-dimensional post-occupancy evaluation (POE) framework to assess primary school buildings' functional and environmental performance. This framework provides a fast and easy tool to evaluate and improve school building performance. To achieve its objective, the study explores different POE models, design components, and functional criteria affecting school building performance. Moreover, it discusses the impact of design parameters such as location, spatial layout, classroom conditions, auxiliary spaces, finishing materials, and environmental elements on building performance. Three main factors were considered: first, child development and well-being, which means meeting the psychological, social, and safety needs of students; second is functional suitability, which means making sure that each part of the building is designed to fulfill its function and works well with other spaces; and thirdly, environmental suitability, which means creating a comfortable space that encourages learning. The research concludes with an evaluation framework with relative and absolute values for school building design parameters in several performance areas. The proposed model enables digital assessment and presents evaluation results both numerically and graphically.

Keywords: Environmental performance, functional performance, post-occupancy evaluation, School building design.

1. INTRODUCTION

The primary goal of constructing any building is to achieve the highest possible return on investment, whether through direct economic gains or as a service-oriented initiative provided by the government or its affiliated entities to meet the city's requirements and the needs of its residents. In the latter case, the primary return is social rather than financial profit (Wang *et al.*, 2024). Maximizing the return on investment for any building involves ensuring optimal utilization throughout its lifespan by enhancing its functional efficiency to the highest degree possible. From this perspective, it becomes crucial to establish an evaluation model to measure the functional efficiency of school buildings for a specific educational stage, in this case, the primary level, considering the differences in functional requirements across various school stages (Hassanain & Mahroos, 2023).

The process of post-occupancy evaluation of the suitability level of proposed school building sites for expected activities involves the following main stages (Adamy & Abu Bakar, 2018):

- *Stage 1:* Identifying the design components that define the characteristics of the school building and the design alternatives that impact its performance (Hadjri & Crozier, 2009).
- *Stage 2:* Establishing performance criteria that reflect the functional and environmental performance of the building and its ability to provide an appropriate school environment (Khalil & Husin, 2009).
- *Stage 3:* Determining the relative importance of each design factor in influencing various aspects of school building performance (Khalil & Husin, 2009).

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- *Stage 4:* Formulating a Performance Evaluation Matrix for the school building, including specific equations for different values, minimum and maximum limits, ratios, and densities for each design factor concerning every functional performance aspect of the school building (Elsayed et al., 2023; Khalil & Husin, 2009).
- *Stage 5:* Developing a model for collecting the school's design data and linking it to the Environmental and Functional Performance Evaluation Matrix. A digital and graphical model will be created to present the school's functional and environmental performance evaluation results while integrating them with the Performance Evaluation Matrix.

Providing a fast and efficient tool that offers direct and practical indicators of the school building's performance in achieving its intended purpose and educational objectives across all functional, environmental, and pedagogical aspects (Hassanain et al., 2022). This tool would be part of the process of enhancing the effectiveness of the existing building while allowing for further studies on the impact of various design factors on the different functional aspects of the school building.

2. SCHOOL BUILDING PERFORMANCE PARAMETERS

Various design and spatial parameters influence the efficiency and performance of a school building, impacting the comfort of its users, including teachers and students. The primary focus is facilitating the educational process, which takes place within the interior and exterior spaces of the building (Takaoka et al., 2015). These elements can be categorized into two main groups:

- *Core Design Parameters:* Directly impact the instructional performance as a fundamental part of the learning process. For example, classrooms serve as the primary spaces for delivering educational content.
- *Supporting Design Parameters:* Influence higher-level educational aspects beyond direct instruction. Contributes to developing students' motor, cognitive, and environmental skills. As an example of such outdoor spaces, play areas, and sports facilities (enhancing physical development). Moreover, libraries and laboratories are essential for supporting cognitive and research skills.
- Common areas and circulation spaces that promote social interaction and movement efficiency.

These design parameters are crucial in shaping the school building's overall functional and environmental performance, ensuring a conducive learning environment (Ariani & Mirdad, 2015).

2.1. School Site Parameters

This includes the nature of the urban surroundings of the school building, which is determined by the following design factors and indicators:

- The nature of the surrounding urban environment (newly planned area–old area–informal settlement–uninhabited area).
- Proximity to environmental pollution sources, such as (cell towers, high-voltage power lines, sewage treatment units, workshops or factories emitting noise or gases, flood paths, areas prone to falling rocks, etc.).
- Ease of access to the school site, considering factors like (flat land, rugged terrain, unpaved roads, garbage accumulation, sewage water, etc.).
- The type of road on which the school building is located (highway–main road–secondary road–local street).
- Availability of a sufficiently wide sidewalk that protects students from oncoming traffic when exiting the school and accommodates the number of students and parents during peak times at the end of the school day.
- Availability of parking spaces within or near the school premises, providing adequate space for school buses and a portion of parents' vehicles without negatively impacting traffic flow on surrounding streets.

2.2. Architectural Layout Aspects

Several building types are commonly used as successful school designs. The following are the commonly utilized by governmental agencies as typical schools (Ariani & Mirdad, 2015):

- *Strip Model:* As shown in Fig 1a, it is a rectangular arrangement of elements, where the corridor may be positioned in the center or on one side. The building length typically ranges between 20 m and 30 m.

Fig. 1. Types of school building composition: a).

- *Finger Model*: A layout where buildings are arranged similarly to the fingers of a hand. The spacing between structures depends on the prevailing climate of the area. As illustrated in Fig. 1b.
- *Courtyard Model*: Fig. 1c shows a design in which school elements are arranged around a single internal courtyard. Orienting openings towards the courtyard can help mitigate noise issues.
- *Multiple Courtyard Model*: A design approach where buildings are grouped around multiple internal courtyards, as shown in Fig. 1d.
- *Compact Model*: A single-building school design that incorporates all elements. The ground floor may be elevated on columns, allowing for an open internal courtyard. as shown in Fig. 1e.

2.3. Floor Number

Floor numbers are crucial for elementary school buildings. It impacts the student's circulation and evacuation in emergency cases. The typical height of the school building is affected by the available area and municipal regulations. According to local education authorities, the maximum number of school buildings is one to four floors.

2.4. School Building Size

The number of classrooms in the building is another factor impacting the design, performance control, and spatial relationship between the primary and supporting components of the design. The minimum school design is one growing class: two preschool classes, six classes, and supporting spaces. In conclusion, local authorities are licensing only schools with a minimum of eight classes and a maximum of forty-eight classes.

2.5. Building Proportions

Building shape and proportion impact its environmental performance. The climatic region of the school building and its orientation are the main factors influencing its form and composition. The preferred ratio between the length and width of the school building varies based on its climatic regions as follows:

- *Hot and humid regions*: The design favors elongation, with a length-to-width ratio 1.7:1, as shown in Fig. 2a.
- *Hot and semi-arid regions*: A more significant difference between length and width is needed, reaching up to 1.5:1, as shown in Fig. 2b.
- *Hot and arid regions*: A more compact form is preferable in the strip model, with a ratio of 1.3:1, as shown in Fig. 2c.

2.6. Building Orientation

Building type and region are the main factors impacting its design and sub-component orientation. Fig. 3 illustrates the best orientation of different types in different climatic regions to achieve the best environmental performance (Khalil & Nawawi, 2008).

2.7. Building Components

In addition to classrooms, the school building contains four different types of spaces to accommodate the functions needed. Educational, supporting services, administration, and open spaces are complimentary spaces. The spatial arrangement of the elements of these types impacts educational facilities' functionality. The following indicators determine the factors (Ariani & Mirdad, 2015; Shakir et al., 2011):

Fig. 2. Orientation and school ratios in different climate regions: a) Best ratio 1:1.7, b) Best ratio 1:1.5, c) Best ratio 1:1.3.

Fig. 3. School building types and orientation for each climatic region.

1. Educational spaces:

- Laboratories (chemistry, physics, biology, computer science, languages)–their capacity and available equipment.
- Art education units (drawing, music, visual arts, vocational workshops, etc.)–their capacity and available equipment.
- Library (size, available furniture, number of books, etc.).
- Student skill development units (school theater, multi-purpose hall, etc.)–their capacity and available equipment.

2. Supporting Service Units:

- Cafeteria (its size, number of tables, size of the supporting kitchen).
- Prayer room (its size, available furnishings and facilities, location of the ablution area, and its suitability for students’ dimensions).
- Healthcare services, including a doctor’s room and an isolation room (its capacity and furnishings).
- Restrooms (number of units, suitability of dimensions for students, distribution across the building’s floors).

3. Administrative spaces are required for managing the educational process:

- Assistant principal’s office–its size and relationship with other building design elements.
- Principal’s office in terms of its size and position relative to other design elements to ensure full supervision of the building.
- Social worker’s office–its size and proximity to classrooms.
- Teachers’ Offices–their number, size, and positioning to facilitate supervision and control over classrooms and student movement.
- Storage Areas–total space, distribution, and variety in sizes.

4. Open Spaces:

- Courtyards (size, type—internal or external, protection from weather conditions).
- Sports Fields (size, location, relationship with other building elements).

Fig. 4. School design components relationship diagram.

2.8. Performance Indicators of Spatial Relationships of Building Elements

Functional considerations play a crucial role in the overall success of a school building. The spatial distribution of school elements, including security, supervision, flexibility, and the smooth movement of materials and equipment, directly influences various functional aspects. Arranging related spaces adjacent to each other (functional proximity) helps streamline operations, positively impacting activities and organizational efficiency (Shakir et al., 2011).

This concept is measured through the degree of functional adjacency, represented in an adjacency matrix. Fig. 4 presents school-building components and their spatial relationships.

2.9. Vertical and Horizontal Circulation Elements (Saudi Building Code, 2022)

Several design factors influence the suitability of horizontal circulation corridors, including (corridor length to stairs or exits, corridor width, type (single or double), style (internal or open to the outside), and dimensions as follows: (SBCNC, 2024)

- Corridors serving one direction with outward-opening doors:
 - 100–500 students: Width between 1.7 m and 2.00 m
 - 500–1000 students: Minimum width of 2.20 m
 - More than 1000 students: Minimum width of 2.50 m
- Corridors serving two directions with outward-opening doors:
 - 100–500 students: Width between 1.7 m and 3.00 m
 - 500–1000 students: Minimum width of 2.20 m
 - More than 1000 students: Minimum width of 2.50 m
- The minimum height of circulation corridors should be 2.30 m
- Door Width Standards:
 - Classroom doors: Minimum width of 0.90 m, minimum height of 2.00 m.
 - Halls accommodating more than 300 students: At least two entrances and two staircases, if not on the ground floor.
 - Halls accommodating more than 800 students: At least three entrances and two staircases.
 - Main exit doors in schools should allow for complete evacuation within 2.5 minutes in case of fire, under international standards.

Fig. 5. Types of class arrangements.

Fig. 6. Viewing angles and class dimensions.

Vertical Circulation Elements: These include stair width, riser height, and the availability of elevators for students with disabilities. Additional considerations include:

- *Stair type:* (Internal–External)
- Staircase position to other building elements.
- Stair width regulations should follow the same width standards as corridors and doors.

Classroom arrangement method: It is preferable to arrange classrooms on one side of the corridor (single-loaded), as this approach ensures adequate lighting and ventilation. The number of classrooms on a single side should not exceed eight, with each classroom ranging between 48–52 m². Fig. 5 presents the different patterns for corridor distribution.

2.10. Classroom Related Aspects

Number of students per classroom and student density (sqm/student): The optimal capacity ranges between 30–35 students, and the student-to-area ratio should have a minimum space of 1.17 m². Classroom width is determined by the distribution of windows on the classroom walls. If windows are placed on one side, the width should not exceed 6.00 m. Simultaneously, classroom height should range between 3.2 m and 4.3 m to ensure proper human scale, adequate natural ventilation, and optimal air circulation. In comparison, Acoustic considerations determine classroom depth. The teacher’s voice should reach at least 68 decibels in the last row. The maximum depth to achieve this is approximately 7 m (Abdelatia et al., 2010). Fig. 6 displays key dimensions, angles, and proportions for optimal visibility and acoustics.

The windowsill height should be at least 1.10 m to prevent students from being distracted by outside activities. A high-level window facing the corridor is preferred to enhance ventilation and air circulation, allow for easy monitoring and supervision, and minimize distractions while maintaining airflow. However, care should be taken as it may contribute to noise transmission. Table I presents

TABLE I: MINIMUM AND OPTIMUM CLASS DIMENSIONS AND STUDENT NUMBERS PER CLASS

Area rate m	Optimum dimensions			Student area m ²	Minimum dimension			Number of students in class
	Height	Width	Length		Height	Width	Length	
1.40	3.20	6.00	8.40	1.17	3.20	5.40	7.80	36
1.44	3.20	7.20	7.20	1.20	3.20	6.60	6.60	36

the ideal and minimum classroom dimensions for elementary schools, along with the recommended space per student, based on studies and international standards, while considering local environmental conditions (Hassanain et al., 2022).

- Interior Finishes (Walls–Floors–Ceilings) may vary in their type and impact on the visual and acoustics characteristics of the classroom. Materials lists include carpet, tiles, ceramic, parquet, etc. Colors, texture, and glossiness level of interior surfaces (Walls–Floors–Ceilings) affect the overall experience of the classroom. Warm colors should be used in areas that attract students’ attention. Surrounding areas should have less attention-grabbing colors to maintain focus. Glossy or reflective surfaces should be avoided to reduce glare and distractions (Ariani & Mirdad, 2015).
- Natural Lighting is an essential aspect of classroom design. Window width, placement, height, and glass type should ensure adequate natural light. Natural lighting should be complemented by artificial lighting throughout the school day. Researchers suggest the illumination level to be not less than 150 lux in the farthest corner of the classroom (Abdelatia et al., 2010).
- Artificial lighting is affected by its type (fluorescent, warm white, etc.) and placement (ceiling-mounted, wall-mounted, etc.). The lighting system should provide uniform illumination across the entire space. A combination of natural and artificial lighting should ensure approximately 300 lux in students’ work areas (Abdelatia et al., 2010; Maciel et al., 2023).
- Providing natural ventilation and temperature control to the classroom’s internal environment significantly influences the students’ experience. Proper window design, wall insulation, and ceiling treatments should help regulate indoor temperatures (H. Sanoff, 2015). Openings should ensure a minimum air exchange rate suitable for different climatic regions. Climate control methods may include central air conditioning, split units, window units, or ceiling fans. The cooling capacity should be appropriately measured in BTUs to ensure a comfortable learning environment (Maciel et al., 2023).

3. ESTABLISHING PERFORMANCE INDICATORS OF SCHOOL BUILDING

Decision-making in the evaluation process is based on predefined indicators aligned with strategic objectives. Establishing evaluation criteria for school buildings plays a key role in assessing their functional and educational performance, helping to clearly understand their capabilities, strengths, and weaknesses (Ahn, 2016). Based on the general functional objectives of a school building and the needs of primary school students, the following indicators have been established:

1. Meeting the Needs of Primary School Children in the School Environment (Ariani & Mirdad, 2015):
 - Supporting children’s cognitive development.
 - Introducing children to their local environment.
 - Providing for children’s physiological needs.
 - Encouraging imagination and creative abilities.
 - Ensuring scale suitability for building dimensions, spaces, and furniture, from restrooms to classrooms, desks, courtyards, and surrounding structures.
 - Ensuring safety from natural hazards (storms, lightning, floods) and human-made risks (electrical units, pollution sources).
 - Enhancing children’s aesthetic awareness.
 - Creating a child-friendly learning environment that integrates play and education.
2. School Functionality Efficiency Aspects (Shakir et al., 2011):
 - Ensuring easy movement between different building components.
 - Establishing strong spatial relationships between functional areas.
 - Providing safety and security for occupants.
 - Protecting the building from external environmental conditions.

- Facilitating supervision and control over building elements and entrances.
- Ensure flexibility in adapting spaces for various activities throughout the day and year.
- Matching space dimensions with functional requirements.
- Designing the building layout to enhance workflow efficiency.
- Considering users' size, number, and height in space planning.
- Allowing building openings and structures to connect effectively with the external environment.
- Ensuring cost-effectiveness in building performance.

3. Environmental Performance and Comfort Levels for Users (Maciel et al., 2023):

- Optimizing natural lighting levels and direction, especially in classrooms.
- Ensuring adequate and well-distributed artificial lighting, with proper intensity at key areas (such as the board and students' desks).
- Providing sufficient natural ventilation through appropriate openings.
- Incorporating temperature control systems for various spaces.
- Protecting the building from external noise pollution.
- Implementing noise reduction strategies to enhance the learning environment and improve student focus.

4. SCHOOL BUILDING PERFORMANCE EVALUATION FRAMEWORK

The proposed framework provides a structured method for assessing the relative impact of different design factors on the functional performance of the building. The environmental and functional performance matrix for school buildings includes various design parameters and indicators of performance aspects. The impact of design parameters on school buildings' performance aspects does not carry the same weight across all evaluation criteria. For example, the "architectural building form" affects multiple performance aspects to varying degrees, such as design flexibility, ease of connectivity between building elements, control over student movement inside the building, exposure to external noise, exposure to environmental factors, and students' connection to the outdoor environment (Kükrer & Eskin, 2021). Each design parameter has a varying level of impact on different performance aspects of the school building. For example, the air conditioning system affects internal noise levels in building spaces, operational cost-efficiency, and the connection of indoor spaces with the external environment. The proposed framework consists of the following structured columns and rows:

- *Columns:* Represent various previously categorized and analyzed design parameters, including different alternatives for each design factor.
- *Rows:* Represent indicators and attributes that define the quality of a school building's functional and environmental performance.

To quantify these differences, the study proposes a five-level grading system for evaluating each design parameter on the performance aspects, where the most influential parameters receive the highest score of five points. In contrast, the less influential factors receive progressively lower scores, down to the least affected aspects, which receive the lowest score of one point. This differentiation helps produce more accurate and credible evaluation results based on whether a particular design factor is met (Zhang & Zhang, 2023).

5. SCHOOL BUILDING PERFORMANCE EVALUATION FRAMEWORK

As shown in Table II, the framework is structured as a matrix, where:

- Rows represent design factors.
- Columns represent performance evaluation aspects.
- Each colored cell represents a relation between the design parameter and the performance aspect. Each of these defined cells contains a value between 1 and 5, indicating the relative importance of the impact of the design parameter on the corresponding evaluation aspect.

A form was developed to collect data for existing school buildings. This form includes a checklist, where users input the information of the site visit via drop-down lists for most selections, allowing users to record values and observations while selecting design alternatives based on the nature of the design factor. By selecting design parameters using the data collection form, the overall impact of each design parameter on each performance aspect is calculated using the formula in (1).

$$Total\ impact\ of\ a\ design\ parameter = Relative\ Impact \times Absolute\ Impact \tag{1}$$

Q3

TABLE II: FRAMEWORK TO EVALUATE DESIGN ASPECTS ON PERFORMANCE INDICATORS

Building information	Building type	Child needs										Functional efficiency										Environmental performance				
		Cognitive development	Physiological needs	Encourage imagination and creativity	Ensure scale suitability	Safety from natural & artificial hazards	Enhance aesthetic awareness	Create learning environment	Exposure to natural environmental	Ensure easy movement	Establish strong spatial relationships	Provide safety and security	Protect from external weather	Supervision and control over elements	Space flexibility and adaptability	Space Suitability for functions' requirements.	Enhanced workflow efficiency	Consider users' size, number, and height	Connect effectively with the external environment	Ensuring cost-effectiveness	Natural lighting	Artificial lighting	Nature ventilation	Climate control	External noise	Internal noise
Classroom	Building type	4	3	3	3	2	4	5	5	5	5	5	4	5	5	3	3	5	5	5	4	4	4	4	5	
	Number of floors	5	5	2	2	2	2	2	5	5	4	4	2	5	5	3	4	5	5	5	3	4	4	5	2	
Classroom	Classes numbers	3	2	3	3	4	4	2	5	2	2	3	3	5	4	2	5	2	5	2	2	2	2	2	2	
	Class dimensions	5	4	5	2	5	3	3	2	2	4	5	5	5	2	5	1	5	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	
Students number	Students number	5	5	4	4	5	3	3	4	5	5	3	3	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	
	Finishings and textures	4	5	5	3	5	5	2	2	2	2	4	5	3	5	4	5	3	5	5	5	5	5	2	2	
Natural lighting and ventilation	Colors	5	4	5	5	5	2	2	2	2	2	4	5	3	5	4	5	4	5	5	2	2	2	5		
	Window dimensions	4	5	3	5	5	3	5	2	2	2	2	2	4	4	1	2	2	2	2	2	3	3	3		
Artificial lighting	Transparency	2	5	3	2	5	2	2	4	3	4	3	4	4	2	4	5	3	3	3	3	5	5	5		
	Artificial lighting	4	5	3	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	4	4	4	4	4	3	5	5	5	5	5	5		
Airconditioning	Airconditioning	2	5	3	2	5	2	5	3	3	3	3	3	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	2		
	Class door width	4	5	4	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	3	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	5	2		

While the overall performance score for the building, the total impact values for each column (representing environmental or functional performance indicators) are summed through (2).

$$\text{Total score for performance indicator} = \sum_{k=1}^n \text{Total impact values for design parameters} \quad (2)$$

The percentage score for each performance aspect is calculated through (3) to obtain standardized performance indicators.

$$\text{Performance indicator percentage score} = \frac{\text{Total score for performance aspect}}{\text{Maximum possible score}} \times 100 \quad (3)$$

6. RESULTS

- Many design components significantly impact the functional efficiency of a school building.
- For a school building to succeed, it must meet children's diverse needs within the school environment while ensuring its various components' environmental and functional compatibility.
- The impact of each design component on different performance aspects can be systematically analyzed.
- Using relative weights for the impact of design components on functional and environmental performance provides a more accurate assessment than using absolute values.
- The proposed framework for primary schools offers quick and direct results, making it a valuable tool for assessment.

7. CONCLUSIONS

The study discussed the post-occupancy evaluation of elementary school buildings. It reviewed the affecting design parameters and the performance indicators. The impact of each design parameter on the different performance aspects was defined. The relative importance of their relationship was estimated. An equation to estimate the overall performance of the school building was formulated in the form of a data collection form that quickly and fatly helped identify the performance gaps and the influencing design aspects. The form was validated in several school buildings. The study is limited to elementary school buildings and the education of children between six and eleven years old. The study paved the way for several future studies. Compare the results of the model with the results of surveying the users; moreover, apply the model to several samples in different locations to evaluate the universality of the framework.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they do not have any conflict of interest.

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